

ANALYZING NEEDS OF LEARNERS IS IMPORTANT REGARDING CREATING CURRICULUM DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: The following Analysis of Needs of Learners is dedicated to developing curriculum in Second Language Acquisition. As the main objectives of this small-scale research are to analyze and identify learners' needs in terms of language learning and help instructors to create more effective courses in terms of second language acquisition. Regarding needs analysis report, several types of research methods are implemented in this research in order to get results that are more reliable.

Keywords: Questionnaire, Curriculum development, Needs analysis report, syllabus

One of the most important component of curriculum development is considered needs analysis. As Richards (2001) defined "need analysis" as a process of collecting information about learner's needs. Additionally, Graves (2000) stated that the aim of needs analysis is to find out what learners know or what they are able to do and what they need to learn or should do. Need analysis can be described as a core element of curriculum development, which involves looking for and elucidate information needs at the end of the course. Needs analysis is consist of several stages which analyze and find out answers to the questions that identify learner's needs. In order to complete Needs Analysis Report, I went to the Uzbekistan State World Languages University and observed several classes there. During the observations, I looked through the syllabus and the curriculum of that university. According to my researches, most of subjects at the university have been organized to shift the students from B1 level to C1 level according to Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR) standard for a four-year academic period. During the research, I mainly observed reading, writing, listening, and speaking classes, which last five or six semesters during four academic years. In addition, we should consider that the lessons usually continue 80 minutes and teachers try to prepare and utilize their lesson plans according to the curriculum, which is confirmed by the government. After observing several classes, I chose one male student because I noticed that he has a lack of English in reading, which is needed to improve. That's why, I chose him and he is a third year student of third English language faculty.

Participant is 23 years old. He and his group mates are fifteen students in the group, two of them are boys, and others are girls. He and his group mates are studying for bachelor`s degree in Foreign language and literature (English language) classes. Moreover, he mentioned that he began to learn English language when he was 15 years old and nowadays his English language proficiency level is intermediate. According to observations, the participant demonstrated good speaking skills during lessons and he mentioned that he prepare his writing tasks considering every detail of each task. However, I admitted that he has a lack of vocabulary building that`s why reading is always complicated skill for him. Therefore, I saw that the teacher and students created positive atmosphere in class, which is very crucial for reaching success in studying. Furthermore, one of the most important thing that I care while doing a research is considering agreement of learner to participate in the survey that is why I explain the learner about what kind of information would be taken from him and what he have to do. I warned him that his personal information could be given in the research and he is supposed to sign a consent form before beginning the survey.

There are several types of procedures, which is useful in collecting needs analysis report. As Richards (2001) stated that procedures, which you utilize in your research are usually associated with the kind of information that you are analyzing. In addition, he advised that it could be beneficial that utilizing two or more types of procedures in the survey, because using single procedure can lead to inaccurate and partial results. After looking through advantages and disadvantages of each procedure, I decided to utilize four instruments to take result that is more accurate in my small-scale research. Firstly, I want to take an interview from the participant in order to collect vital information about personality traits, goals, and interests of the learner. That`s why I made a list of questions, which investigates learner`s goals, learning style and strategies, and personality. Additionally, one of beneficial side of interview is that researcher can identify accurate issues in the process of face-to-face interview. Secondly, I utilize questionnaire which consists of 6 items that identify learner`s difficulties and weaknesses of learner in learning process. Questionnaire is adapted from Marshall (2002) and it is outlined to find out needs of intermediate and advanced level learner. One of the advantages of questionnaire is that it would give a chance to learners to analyze and evaluate their weaknesses. Additionally, I wanted to correlate the questionnaire with self-rating test, which consists of 20 items, and the procedure is helpful to clarify weaknesses in-depth during the

research. Moreover, self-rating is considered as one of effective instrument to determine learner's abilities and knowledge based on four skills. Finally, the most important tool which is utilized in this research is a sample of learner's writing because a piece of learner's writing work can clarify accurate needs of the learner. Therefore, I prepared a task in which learner have to write a letter that consists of 150 words and it should be informal letter. After analyzing needs of learner by utilizing different procedures, it became clear that the participant has a good productive skill in English language. Moreover, the participant is not only visual learner but also he has improved his listening skills. Although the participant utilized some reading strategies in learning process, he has some problems with his reading skills because of a lack of vocabulary building. Correlation of all used procedures shows that learner's urgent needs is to improve both reading skills and vocabulary building. According to my viewpoint, these problems can be solved by practicing and learning words daily. If I conducted this group or student, I would have taught vocabulary in context because by this way learners can spontaneously recall words and reading for meaning can also be effective for improving vocabulary knowledge. In addition, it is advisable that a teacher should utilize appropriate materials according to learner level and needs considering syllabus and curriculum requirement.

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